

Comparison of social quality criteria in building sustainability certification systems

Research Team

Anna Elisabeth Kristoffersen
Ph.D. Student
Building science
CAE, Aarhus University
Email: aek@cae.au.dk

Aliakbar Kamari
Assit. Prof., Ph.D.
Building science
CAE, Aarhus University
Email: ak@cae.au.dk

Steffen Petersen
Professor, Ph.D.
Building science
CAE, Aarhus University
Email: stp@cae.au.dk

Introduction

Background

- Growing demand for sustainable development throughout society
- Sustainability is often evaluated based on the so-called three pillars of sustainability: Environmental, Economic and Social Sustainability
- Previous comparisons of building certification schemes focused on criteria weighting and point distribution without considering any similarities and differences between the criteria themselves

Investigation

- What are the similarities and differences of social-oriented criteria in major building certification schemes?

Method

Deconstruction of the criteria grouping of four major building certification systems. Identification of similarities and differences between criteria. Regrouping of the criteria based on whether the criteria 1) is focused on social quality as perceived by building users, and 2) can be impacted by the building design team.

Conclusion

The social-oriented qualities addressed in the four certification systems can be regrouped into the following common categories:

- Thermal comfort
- Indoor air quality
- Acoustics
- Daylight and electric light
- Human health
- Miscellaneous

The criteria of the four certification systems are thus, to a wide extent, similar both in terms of social qualities that are addressed and how these qualities are evaluated; however, benchmarks for evaluation are adapted to local conditions. Therefore, the difference of the systems is not due to the inclusion of more or less social-oriented criteria but merely the weighting hereof.

Results

Thermal comfort

Indoor air quality

Acoustics

Daylight and electric light

Human health

Miscellaneous

